

Bradford HDRC Policy Brief

Addressing Childhood Vulnerability, Crime and Justice

Target Audience: Local Authorities

Based on N8 Child of the North Report - An evidence-based plan for addressing childhood vulnerability, crime and justice

CotN_Crime-justice_Report_11.pdf

Key Evidence Based Messages

- **Adopt whole-child and whole-system** approaches to childhood vulnerability. Attention and focus must be on need and putting children and families at the centre of coordinated services. Doing so can identify and address the reasons why children offend or become the victims of crime and thus support those young people to flourish.
- **Tackle underlying vulnerabilities and disadvantages** that are often driving young people into the criminal justice system such as exclusion in the context of school
- **National level focus:**
 - Place children at the heart of service provision focused on the whole child. Services must work together to create responsive and supportive networks for young people, especially those impacted by adverse childhood experiences.
 - Policy and practice should focus on addressing underlying vulnerabilities and disadvantages not behaviour: aim to keep out rather than bring in to the youth justice system.
 - Focus on prevention and upstream health, social and educational programmes. The goal is to keep out rather than bring in to the CJS.
- **Local level focus:**
 - Develop child first and restorative practices.
 - Focus partnership working on collaborative prevention and early intervention.
 - Tailor place-based approaches around localities.

The Problem: Children’s involvement in the criminal justice system or become victims of serious violence or crime. Most children involved in the criminal justice system share very similar experiences of childhood adversity

1 in 4 surveyed 13-17-year-olds said they’d been either victim or perpetrator of violence

3 in 4 young people feel they lack the digital skills to thrive

While 94% of looked after children in England and Wales do not get into trouble with the law, approximately half of children in custody have previously been in care at some point.

“[The statistics are a] sobering reminder of the work we collectively need to do to address disproportionality, find and use alternatives to remand, and to keep children out of the justice system”

- Chair of the Youth Justice Board

“Above all, we must always remember that youth justice statistics are about children, their lives, their trauma and their needs which we, collectively, must meet.”

- Chair of the Youth Justice Board

What you can do at a local level

- **Place children at the heart of service provision and consider the “whole child”:** A holistic and coordinated “whole-system” approach means public services working together to identify and address the reasons why children offend or become victims of crime. Partnerships with local health services and community organisations would further strengthen this approach by bringing a wider range of expertise together, creating a holistic, “whole-system” safety net.
- **Promote prevention and upstream health, social and educational programmes:** for children, young people, their families, and communities to keep young people out of the criminal justice system through diversion schemes. Schools should be supported to collaborate with local organisations capable of offering extracurricular programmes that build skills, self-worth, and community connection.
- **Adopting Place-based approaches:** approaches to addressing vulnerability and crime must be planned and aligned to the needs and preferences of a locality and its communities, considering the social and economic circumstances.
- **Developing child-first and restorative approaches** in local youth justice practice that centres on needs, rights, and wellbeing of children at all stages of Youth Justice. This can help keep children out of the CJS.

Approaches trialled in practice

Example	Approach	Impact
Child First approaches for violence reduction	West Yorkshire Violence Reduction Partnership (VRP), a focus on “child first” has grown into a region-wide meaningful collaboration with children across West Yorkshire in violence reduction work.	Adoption of a child first approach in local youth justice practice, centring the needs, rights, and wellbeing of children at every stage of Youth Justice.
Risk Outside the Home (ROTH) Pathway	Based on “Contextual Safeguarding”, this articulates the risks of gaps in local systems, and pilots alternative pathway in cases that included responses to criminal exploitation of young people. Concerns about “youth violence” were addressed through re-situating social work within communities.	Frame criminal justice responses to extra-familial harm as secondary to safeguarding responses. Address youth violence through social work in communities. Create relationships with non-statutory and community partners as a common feature of the practice
Bradford SAFE Taskforce	A variety of designed, evidence-based interventions were introduced across 18 schools in Bradford. The primary focus was to improve children’s attendance, behaviour, and engagement with their education.	Improved attendance, reduced suspensions and improved behaviour. First year showed improvement in attendance and reduction in suspensions. Suspension Rate for SAFE Taskforce schools for academic year 2023-24 stood at 64.1% compared to 80.4% for the full academic year 2022-23.
Safer Parks: Improving access for women and girls	The Safer Parks Consortium – a partnership of the University of Leeds, West Yorkshire Combined Authority, Make Space for Girls, and Keep Britain Tidy - developed new guidelines aimed at making parks safer and more welcoming for women and girls.	Co-designed parks to address intersectional needs. Guidance provides practical examples of how to implement changes on different budgets and scales and has been incorporated into the Green Flag Award programme, which sets the standard for public parks and green spaces in the UK and globally.
Getting Out for Good	GOFG is a rigorous five-year research project exploring the experiences of over 100 girls and young women at risk of sexual exploitation and gang involvement. It offered mentoring with sporting and cultural activities for girls and young women referred into the project.	Enhanced sporting activities for young women to contribute towards resilience building, enhancing personal aspirations, facilitating teamwork, and fostering positive peer networks. Project also up-skilled young women who participated for the job market with nationally recognised AQA qualifications, in partnership with Manchester Metropolitan University.